

3- β -NAPHTHYL-2 : 4-THIAZOLIDIONE AND ITS DERIVATIVES

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3- β -Naphthyl-2:4-thiazolidione, prepared from *s*-di- β -naphthylthiourea and monochloroacetic acid in presence of glacial acetic acid along with concentrated HCl, has been condensed with eight aldehydes and three aryldiazonium chlorides; its degradation products as well as characteristic reactions leading to various derivatives have been studied.

Markley and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2137) studied the secondary formation of 3-phenyl-2:4-thiazolidione along with the primary formation of 3-phenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone, when *s*-diphenylthiourea was treated with monochloroacetic acid in alcoholic medium. In view of the close relationship between thiazolidones and thiazolidiones and the reported uses of thiazolidone compounds as anaesthetics (Surrey, *ibid.*, 1949, 71, 3105), amoebacidal agents (Surrey and Cutler, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 578) and anticonvulsants (Troutman and Long, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 3436), it was considered worthwhile to prepare 3- β -naphthyl-2:4-thiazolidione in continuation to the earlier work on 3-*o*-tolyl- and 3-*p*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidiones and their derivatives by Bhargava *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 463; 1956, 33, 596). Its properties, degradation products as well as characteristic group reactions have been studied.

In the present investigation, the compound has been prepared by the interaction of *s*-di- β -naphthylthiourea and monochloroacetic acid in presence of glacial acetic acid (or absolute alcohol) along with strong hydrochloric acid.

During studies on the effect of reaction conditions on the preparation of 3- β -naphthyl-2:4-thiazolidione, the highest yield (36%) is obtained when 10 c.c. of glacial acetic acid per 6.5 g. of *s*-di- β -naphthylthiourea and 2.5 g. of monochloroacetic acid are employed and the time of reflux for 10 hours is maintained. On increasing the period of reflux for more than 12 hours, a decrease in the yield is indicated owing to the decomposition and subsequent resinification.

The structure of the compound has been confirmed by the synthesis of 3- β -naphthyl-2- β -naphthylimino-4-thiazolidone and its subsequent hydrolysis to 3- β -naphthyl-3:4-thiazolidione in acid medium.

The compound, on boiling with potassium hydroxide solution, has yielded β -naphthylamine and thiolacetic acid, and on fusion with sodalime, β -naphthylamine, which has been identified by the preparation of its azo- β -naphthol derivative.

The reactive methylene group of the compound has been successfully condensed with eight aldehydes and three aryldiazonium chlorides, forming respectively 5-arylidene- and 5-aryldiazo-2:4-thiazolidiones. The assumption that the azo group is attached to the thiazolidione nucleus in position-5 is based on the observations of Bogert and Chertcoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2864; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1924, 10, 418).

They obtained dyes by coupling diazotised *p*-nitroaniline and sulphanic acid with 2-aminothiazole, from which they concluded that the azo group was attached to position-5 of the thiazole nucleus. On account of the close relationship among thiazole, thiazolidone and thiazolidione, similar behaviour is also expected in the case of the present thiazolidione.

Further, on oxidation with potassium permanganate in glacial acetic acid according to Turner *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 1986), 3- β -naphthyl-2:4-thiazolidione sulphone has been obtained, as established by analytical data corresponding to the addition of two atoms of oxygen to the thiazolidione.

EXPERIMENTAL

3- β -Naphthyl-2:4-thiazolidione.—A mixture of *s*-di- β -naphthylthiourea (6.5 g.), monochloroacetic acid (2.5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (10–15 c.c.) along with HCl (conc., 5–10 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 3–12 hours and then allowed to cool. Addition of water in moderate excess gave a white precipitate and a resinous mass. The precipitate was separated by boiling the solution and filtering through a hot water funnel. When the clear solution was cooled to room temperature, 3- β -naphthyl-2:4-thiazolidione was reprecipitated. This was allowed to settle, filtered and crystallised from hot water. The product was found to melt at 181°. A series of experiments were carried out by varying the time of reflux, but the highest yield obtained was 36%, when the time of reflux was 10 hours. On increasing the time of reflux to more than 12 hours, the product decomposed and resinified. (Found: N, 5.68; S, 13.26. C₁₃H₉O₂NS requires N, 5.76; S, 13.17%). It is soluble in hot water but insoluble in cold water. It is readily soluble in glacial acetic acid, alcohol, benzene and toluene in cold.

Decomposition with KOH into β -Naphthylamine and Thiolacetic Acid.—Thiazolidione (1 g.) was boiled under reflux with 40% KOH (50 c.c.) on a water-bath for 2½ hours. After the reaction, it was cooled, filtered, washed with water and dried. On crystallisation from alcohol, the substance corresponding to β -naphthylamine melted at 110°. It was finally confirmed by the preparation of its azo- β -naphthol derivative, m.p. 174°

The filtrate on neutralisation with acid exhibited a transient blue colour with FeCl₃ and purple colour with dilute sodium hydroxide and sodium nitroprusside, characteristic of thiolacetic acid.

3- β -Naphthyl-5-benzylidene-2:4-thiazolidione.—A mixture of thiazolidione (0.5 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.), benzaldehyde (2 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) was heated under reflux in an oil-bath at 140–50° for 3½ hours. The contents after the reaction solidified as a colorless cake. It was filtered, washed with water, glacial acetic acid and alcohol, and dried. On crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, colorless crystals were obtained.

Similarly other aldehydes were condensed yielding 5-arylidene derivatives. The properties and analytical data are recorded in Table I,

TABLE I

3-β-Naphthyl-5-arylidene-2:4-thiazolidione.

No.	Nature of aldehyde condensed.	% Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Benzaldehyde	75	Colorless	229°	9.59	9.67
2.	Salicylaldehyde	55	Brown	236°	9.10	9.22
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	82	Greenish yellow	253°	8.67	8.75
4.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	60	Brownish yellow	260°	8.42	8.51
5.	Anisaldehyde	62	Pale yellow	174°	8.82	8.86
6.	Piperonal	90	Grey	219°	8.57	8.53
7.	Furfural	45	Black	280° (dec. mp.)	9.86	9.91
8.	Cinnamaldehyde	42	Yellow	210°	9.04	8.96

3-β-Naphthyl-5-o-tolueneazo-2:4-thiazolidione.—*o*-Toluidine (6 c.c.) in HCl (conc., 20 c.c.) was diazotised with an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (20 c.c.) and to this a solution of thiazolidione (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) was slowly added at 0° while stirring and was kept in an ice-bath for 1 hour. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with water and alcohol. On crystallisation from alcohol orange-red crystals were obtained.

Similarly, the thiazolidione was condensed with benzenediazonium chloride and *p*-toluenediazonium chloride. The properties of these compounds and their analytical data are reported in Table II.

TABLE II

3-β-Naphthyl-5-aryldiazo-2:4-thiazolidione.

No.	Diazonium chloride of amines.	Colour.	M.P.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
1	Aniline	Deep brown	154°	9.31	9.26
2	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Orange-red	173°	8.34	8.86
3	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Light yellow	210°	8.37	8.86

3-β-Naphthyl-2:4-thiazolidione Sulphone.—*3-β-Naphthyl-2:4-thiazolidione* (0.5 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.), was treated slowly with KMnO₄ (1 g.), dissolved in water (40 c.c.) at 0°. After the reaction, excess of permanganate was removed by treatment with sodium bisulphite. The sulphone was filtered, washed with ice-water, dried and crystallised from alcohol into a colorless form, m.p. 176° (decomp.). Found: S, 11.79. C₁₃H₉O₄NS requires S, 11.64%.